

Abstraction Logic: A New Foundation

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Abstract. Abstraction logic is a logic designed to bridge the gap between informal and formal mathematical reasoning. The key innovation lies in its ability to simultaneously support general binders and maintain a single mathematical universe—two features that have traditionally appeared incompatible in formal logic. This is achieved by carefully distinguishing between mathematical objects, operations, and operators. A comprehensive theory of abstraction logic is presented, including its algebraic foundations, a semantic account of alpha equivalence, and sound proof systems for both natural deduction and sequent calculus. Furthermore, natural deduction is shown to be complete.

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1 Motivation

The purpose of this paper is to introduce *abstraction logic*. A detailed technical report on abstraction logic is available [1], and this paper is its condensed version. We give a full account of the theory of abstraction logic so far, referring to the report for technical but straightforward results and proofs.

The purpose of abstraction logic is to narrow the gulf between the formal and the informal. Why is there such a gulf in the first place, even when considering only people highly trained in precise thinking, such as mathematicians? Intuitively, one assumes that the shift from informal reasoning to formal reasoning is merely a shift in precision, where all assumptions and deduction steps are clearly laid out. Yet, current logical foundations—such as first-order logic, second-order logic, simply-typed higher-order logic or dependently-typed higher-order logic—do not seem to facilitate this shift of precision as smoothly as one might expect. Our work on abstraction logic has led us to believe that there is a simple, almost mundane explanation for this: a logic must support both *general binders* and a *single mathematical universe*, two features which appear to be in opposition but surprisingly can be reconciled.

By **general binders**, we mean the ability to introduce and work with arbitrary variable binding constructs.

Example 1. There are many examples of such constructs in informal reasoning:

1. There is an x such that $P[x]$ holds.
2. For all x and y , where $x < y$, we have that $P[x, y]$ holds.
3. Choose x such that $P[x]$ is true.
4. Sum up all $F[i]$, where i ranges over all natural numbers such that $n \leq i \leq m$.
5. Let f be the function that maps x to x^2 , where x is a real number.

General binders are supported by typed higher-order logics, but they are not supported by either first-order or second-order logic, which both support only universal quantification (“For all...”) and existential quantification (“There is...”). Later, Example 2 expresses the above formally using abstraction algebra.

By a **single mathematical universe**, we mean that we are working with a single universe that encompasses *all mathematical objects*. In informal discourse, one assumes such a homogeneous playing field implicitly; the very phrase *mathematical object* is revealing, as it implies the existence of a *space* of mathematical objects. Mathematical objects can be combined freely to form other mathematical objects. An expression such as $e^{i\pi} + 1$ makes sense without any further annotations, although it contains a mix of natural numbers, real numbers and complex numbers. One can talk about sets or lists of arbitrary mathematical objects, and there is no need to interact with a complicated type system in order to do so. First-order logic and second-order logic feature a single mathematical universe, while higher-order logic (HOL), both simply-typed and dependently typed, does not. HOL cannot support a single mathematical universe because of Cantor’s theorem [1, p. 4]. This is because HOL treats functions on mathematical objects as mathematical objects themselves. Yet Cantor’s theorem informs us that this is impossible in general, as there are many more such functions than there are mathematical objects. To escape this paradox, HOL employs an infinite tower $\mathcal{U}_\infty = \bigcup_{i \in \mathbb{N}} \mathcal{U}_i$ of universes \mathcal{U}_i , where the functions on the mathematical objects of \mathcal{U}_i are among the mathematical objects of \mathcal{U}_{i+1} . Of course, the tower is strictly contained in the *actual* mathematical universe \mathcal{U} , as \mathcal{U} additionally includes all mathematical objects that are functions on \mathcal{U}_∞ (Figure 1a).

The example of HOL seems to show that when it comes to formal logic, general binders are in opposition to a single mathematical universe. But this is not so. Abstraction logic manages to combine both features harmoniously. All it takes to achieve this is to acknowledge that, in general, *operations* are not mathematical objects. Here, an operation is a function that takes mathematical objects as arguments and returns a mathematical object as its result. With this acknowledgement, we sidestep Cantor’s theorem, but now we face a new problem: how do we talk about operations? In HOL, this problem does not exist, as operations within \mathcal{U}_∞ are simply mathematical objects, and operations outside \mathcal{U}_∞ do not exist from HOL’s perspective. In abstraction logic, the solution is the introduction of *operators*. An operator is a function that takes operations as its arguments and returns a mathematical object as its result. The situation is depicted in Figure 1b.

Fig. 1: Tower of universes vs. single mathematical universe

2 Overview

We have argued that general binders and a single mathematical universe are features of informal reasoning, and that both can be achieved in formal reasoning simultaneously by adhering to a simple understanding of the mathematical universe, its operations, and its operators. The rest of this paper describes how to do so and explores its surprisingly far-reaching consequences.

Section 3 introduces a simple and elegant formal language for describing and working with mathematical objects, operations, and operators, called *abstraction algebra*, as a natural extension of *abstract algebra*. After presenting its syntax and semantics, we define *alpha equivalence* purely semantically as a notion that captures the idea that two expressions of the language mean the same under any circumstances. Using *de Bruijn indices*, we construct the *de Bruijn abstraction algebra* and show that alpha equivalence has the familiar alternative characterisation that is purely syntactic and easily computable. Essential tools used in the proof are *substitution* and *evaluation*, and how they relate to each other.

Section 4 shows how to build *abstraction logic* on top of abstraction algebra. Formulas are merely terms, because *truth values* form a partially ordered substructure within the mathematical universe. If truth values constitute a complete lattice, then (what we call) *natural deduction* is a sound proof system for abstraction logic. Furthermore, if they form a bi-Heyting algebra, (what we call) *sequent calculus* is also sound. By constructing the *Rasiowa model*, we see that natural deduction is a complete proof system for abstraction logic.

Section 5 concludes with an example of a concrete abstraction logic for intuitionistic predicate calculus.

3 Abstraction Algebra

We assume a **mathematical universe** \mathcal{U} , in which our **mathematical objects** reside. We also refer to these mathematical objects as **values**. They are combined via *operations*. And operations are combined via *operators*.

Definition 1. *An n -ary operation on \mathcal{U} is a function that accepts n values from \mathcal{U} as inputs and yields a single value from \mathcal{U} as its output. A nullary operation is simply a value.*

Definition 2. *An n -ary operator on \mathcal{U} is a function that accepts n operations on \mathcal{U} as inputs and yields a single value from \mathcal{U} as its output. Each input position i of the operator accepts only operations of a fixed arity m_i . The list $[m_1, \dots, m_n]$ is referred to as the **shape** of the operator.*

A mathematical universe \mathcal{U} together with a collection of operations on \mathcal{U} is called an **abstract algebra** [2, p.287]. Given that in our setting we are considering not only values and operations, but also operators, it is natural to introduce the following generalisation of abstract algebras.

Definition 3. *An **abstraction algebra** \mathcal{A} is a universe \mathcal{U} together with a collection \mathcal{O} of operators on \mathcal{U} .*

3.1 Syntax

An *abstraction* is simply a name standing for an operator of a certain shape. We are usually not interested just in a single abstraction, but in a collection of abstractions and their interplay.

Definition 4. *A **signature** \mathfrak{S} is a collection of names called **abstractions**, where each abstraction is associated with a shape. A **\mathfrak{S} -algebra** is an abstraction algebra \mathcal{A} together with a signature \mathfrak{S} such that each abstraction of \mathfrak{S} is associated with an operator of \mathcal{A} of the same shape. We often do not distinguish between the \mathfrak{S} -algebra and its abstraction algebra.*

Assume an infinite collection \mathcal{X} of **variables**, which we keep fixed throughout. Given a signature \mathfrak{S} , we can define a **language** for expressing values and operations abstractly without referring to any concrete abstraction algebra. We describe values via *terms*, and operations via *templates*.

Definition 5. *A **term** is either a variable application or an abstraction application. A **variable application (of arity n)** is written $x[t_1, \dots, t_n]$. Here $x \in \mathcal{X}$ is a variable, and the t_i are terms. For $n = 0$ we usually write x instead of $x[]$. An **abstraction application** is written $(aT_1 \dots T_n)$. Here a is an abstraction of shape $[m_1, \dots, m_n]$, and the T_i are templates of arity m_i . We may drop the brackets when no ambiguity can arise. A **template (of arity n)** is written $(b_1 \dots b_n.t)$. Here the $b_i \in \mathcal{X}$ are n distinct variables, and t is a term. A template of arity 0 is just a term. Again, we may drop the brackets when there is no ambiguity to fear.*

Terms and templates only make sense relative to a given signature \mathfrak{S} . When we want to emphasise this, we also speak of \mathfrak{S} -terms and \mathfrak{S} -templates.

Example 2. It is straightforward to translate our previous informal Example 1 into the formal language of abstraction algebra:

1. exists $(x. P[x])$
2. for-all $(x y. \text{implies } (\text{less } x y) P[x, y])$
3. choose $(x. P[x])$
4. nat-sum $n m (i. F[i])$
5. equals f (function real-numbers $(x. \text{mul } x x)$)

The signature in which these expressions are formulated contains the abstractions ‘exists’ and ‘choose’ of shape [1], ‘for-all’ of shape [2], ‘implies’, ‘less’, ‘equals’ and ‘mul’ of shape [0, 0], ‘nat-sum’ of shape [0, 0, 1], ‘function’ of shape [0, 1], and ‘real-numbers’ of shape []. In the future, we will not spell out the shapes of abstractions explicitly anymore, as they are apparent from their usage in expressions. The meaning of these abstractions is intended to be obvious according to their names, but formally and without any further constraints, these abstractions range over all operators of appropriate shapes. Note that while ‘function’ itself denotes a proper operator, and not a mathematical object, its applications, which are meant to be functions, *do* denote mathematical objects.

3.2 Semantics

Definition 6. Let \mathcal{A} be an abstraction algebra, and \mathcal{U} its universe. A **valuation** ν *into* \mathcal{A} is a mapping assigning to each variable $x \in \mathcal{X}$ and each arity n an n -ary operation $\nu(x, n)$ on \mathcal{U} .

Note that the operation $\nu(x, n)$ does not have to be an operator of \mathcal{A} , but can be any n -ary operation on \mathcal{U} .

Definition 7. For a given valuation ν into \mathcal{A} , distinct variables x_1, \dots, x_k , and values u_1, \dots, u_k in \mathcal{U} , the **valuation update** $\nu[x_1 := u_1, \dots, x_k := u_k]$ is also a valuation into \mathcal{A} , defined by

$$\nu[x_1 := u_1, \dots, x_k := u_k](y, n) = \begin{cases} u_i & \text{for } y = x_i \text{ and } n = 0, \\ \nu(y, n) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

An update only affects the output of the valuation for variables at arity 0.

A \mathfrak{S} -algebra provides meaning for the abstractions of a term, and for its *bound* variables, while a valuation provides meaning for its *free* variables. Together, they provide meaning for the entire term.

Definition 8. Given a \mathfrak{S} -algebra \mathcal{A} , and a valuation ν into \mathcal{A} , we define the **evaluation** $\llbracket T \rrbracket_\nu$ of a \mathfrak{S} -template T recursively over its structure:

1. For a template $T = (b_1 \dots b_n.t)$, $n \geq 1$, we define the n -ary operation $\llbracket T \rrbracket_\nu$

$$\llbracket T \rrbracket_\nu(u_1, \dots, u_n) = \llbracket t \rrbracket_\mu$$

for all values u_1, \dots, u_n in the universe of \mathcal{A} , where

$$\mu = \nu[b_1 := u_1, \dots, b_n := u_n].$$

2. For a variable application $t = x[t_1, \dots, t_n]$, we define

$$\llbracket t \rrbracket_\nu = \nu(x, n)(\llbracket t_1 \rrbracket_\nu, \dots, \llbracket t_n \rrbracket_\nu).$$

3. For an abstraction application $t = aT_1 \dots T_n$, we define

$$\llbracket t \rrbracket_\nu = o(\llbracket T_1 \rrbracket_\nu, \dots, \llbracket T_n \rrbracket_\nu),$$

where o is the operator associated with the abstraction a in \mathcal{A} .

Thus, evaluating a template of arity n yields an n -ary operation. In particular, evaluating a term yields a value.

3.3 Alpha Equivalence and Alpha Conversion

An important link between syntax and semantics is established through the notion of *alpha equivalence*.

Definition 9. Two \mathfrak{S} -templates S and T are **alpha equivalent** iff they have the same arity, and for all \mathfrak{S} -algebras \mathcal{A} and all valuations ν into \mathcal{A} , $\llbracket S \rrbracket_\nu = \llbracket T \rrbracket_\nu$.

From our definition it is immediately clear that alpha equivalence is indeed an equivalence relation among all \mathfrak{S} -templates, i.e. it is reflexive, symmetric, and transitive.

Example 3. The terms `exists` $(x.P[x])$ and `exists` $(y.P[y])$ are alpha equivalent. This is because $\llbracket \text{exists } (x.P[x]) \rrbracket_\nu = o(\nu(P, 1)) = \llbracket \text{exists } (y.P[y]) \rrbracket_\nu$ in any abstraction algebra \mathcal{A} and any valuation ν into \mathcal{A} , where o is the operator associated with ‘exists’ in \mathcal{A} . On the other hand, the terms `exists` $(x.P[x])$ and `exists` $(x.Q[x])$ are not alpha equivalent. To see this, pick any abstraction algebra and valuation such that $o(\nu(P, 1)) \neq o(\nu(Q, 1))$.

Alpha equivalence of two terms or templates means that their meaning is always the same, no matter which \mathfrak{S} -algebra \mathcal{A} and valuation into \mathcal{A} are considered. While we have therefore defined alpha equivalence as a purely semantic notion, we will see that alpha equivalence is *also* a purely syntactic notion, and can easily be computed. Indeed, in the literature, alpha equivalence is always introduced as a syntactic notion, and it is remarkable that in abstraction algebra, the most straightforward way to introduce alpha equivalence is to do it as a semantic notion.

In abstraction algebra, the key to view alpha equivalence as a syntactic notion is through the introduction of *de Bruijn terms*. De Bruijn terms do not use variables to refer to template parameters; instead, they use *de Bruijn indices*.

Definition 10. A *de Bruijn term* is either a de Bruijn index, a variable application, or an abstraction application. A *de Bruijn index* is simply a number $i \in \mathbb{N}$, and is written $\uparrow i$. A *variable application (of arity n)* is written $x[t_1, \dots, t_n]$. Here $x \in \mathcal{X}$ is a variable, and the t_i are de Bruijn terms. For $n = 0$ we usually write x instead of $x[]$. An *abstraction application* is written $(\lambda t_1 \dots t_n)$. Here λ is an n -ary abstraction, and the t_i are de Bruijn terms. We may drop the brackets when no ambiguity can arise.

Compared to Definition 5, what stands out is that the definition of de Bruijn terms does not rely on an explicit notion of templates. A de Bruijn ‘template’ is simply a de Bruijn term with (possibly) *dangling* de Bruijn indices.

It is then possible to convert a template T into a de Bruijn term $\alpha(T)$. We will not go into the details of this here, it works as one would expect it to work¹, and an example will suffice.

Example 4. Let T be the template

$$x y. \text{ implies } (\text{less } x y) (\text{exists } (z. \text{ and } (\text{less } x z) (\text{less } z y))).$$

Then its alpha conversion $\alpha(T)$ is

$$\text{implies } (\text{less } \uparrow 0 \uparrow 1) (\text{exists } (\text{and } (\text{less } \uparrow 1 \uparrow 0) (\text{less } \uparrow 0 \uparrow 2))),$$

which has the **dangling indices** $\uparrow 0$ and $\uparrow 1$.

We say that a de Bruijn term t has **arity** n iff for all dangling indices $\uparrow i$ of t , we have $i < n$. In Example 4, $\alpha(T)$ has arity 2 and higher, but not arity 0 or 1. In general, the alpha conversion of an n -ary template has arity n . This means that the alpha conversion of a term has arity 0, and therefore no dangling indices. We write \mathcal{T} for the collection of all de Bruijn terms, with respect to a given signature. And we write \mathcal{T}_n for the collection of all de Bruijn terms of arity n .

The following theorem shows that alpha conversion is the syntactic incarnation of alpha equivalence we were alluding to earlier.

Theorem 1. *Two \mathfrak{S} -templates S and T are alpha equivalent iff they have the same arity and $\alpha(S) = \alpha(T)$.*

The full proof of this theorem occupies most of the second chapter of [1], culminating in [1, p. 69, Theorem 2.10]. The proof is straightforward, but long, because it needs to develop the required technical basis of abstraction algebra first. We will not go into all of the details here, pointing out only those particulars needed in the context of this paper.

It is easy to see that if S and T have the same alpha conversion, then they are also alpha equivalent [1, p. 25, Corollary 2.2]. It remains to be shown that alpha equivalent templates have the same alpha conversion.

¹ See [1, p. 20, Definition 2.18] for those details.

3.4 Substitution and Evaluation

Definition 11. A \mathfrak{S} -*substitution* is a partial function σ mapping pairs (x, n) , consisting of a variable $x \in \mathcal{X}$ and arity $n \in \mathbb{N}$, to an n -ary \mathfrak{S} -template $\sigma(x, n)$.

A *pure de Bruijn \mathfrak{S} -substitution* is a partial function σ mapping de Bruijn indices to de Bruijn \mathfrak{S} -terms.

In both cases we write the application of a substitution σ to a template or de Bruijn term t as t/σ . Pure de Bruijn substitutions let us state what it means to apply a de Bruijn term $f \in \mathcal{T}_n$ to n de Bruijn terms $t_1, \dots, t_n \in \mathcal{U}$, yielding a term in \mathcal{U} , where for our purposes \mathcal{U} is either \mathcal{T} or \mathcal{T}_0 :

$$f[t_1, \dots, t_n] = f/\{\uparrow 0 \mapsto t_1, \dots, \uparrow(n-1) \mapsto t_n\}.$$

We can apply a substitution not only to templates, but also to valuations:

$$\nu_\sigma(x, n) = \begin{cases} \llbracket \sigma(x, n) \rrbracket_\nu & \text{for } (x, n) \text{ in the domain of } \sigma \\ \nu(x, n) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Substitution and evaluation are then related as follows [1, p. 65, Theorem 2.9]:

Theorem 2. $\llbracket T \rrbracket_{\nu_\sigma} = \llbracket T/\sigma \rrbracket_\nu$.

3.5 De Bruijn Abstraction Algebra

For each signature \mathfrak{S} , we construct its corresponding **de Bruijn abstraction algebra** (which has signature \mathfrak{S}). Its universe \mathcal{U} is either \mathcal{T} or \mathcal{T}_0 , the construction works for either case. Next, we define its operators.

Definition 12. For each $h \in \mathbb{N}$, we introduce the function $\Gamma_h : \mathcal{T}_h \rightarrow (\mathcal{U}^h \rightarrow \mathcal{U})$ which converts any de Bruijn term t of arity h into an h -ary operation on \mathcal{U} :

$$\Gamma_h(t)(u_1, \dots, u_h) = t[u_1, \dots, u_h] \quad \text{for all } u_1, \dots, u_h \in \mathcal{U}.$$

Because Γ_h is injective [1, p. 66, Lemma 2.31], we can define for each abstraction $a \in \mathfrak{S}$ of shape $[m_1, \dots, m_n]$ its associated operator o as follows:

$$o(\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n) = \begin{cases} a t_1 \dots t_n & \text{where } \gamma_i = \Gamma_{m_i}(t_i), \\ x & \text{if for some } \gamma_i \text{ no such } t_i \text{ exists.} \end{cases}$$

The choice of $x \in \mathcal{X}$ for the second case is arbitrary and without significance.

Definition 13. The *canonical valuation* κ is defined as

$$\kappa(x, n)(u_1, \dots, u_n) = x[u_1, \dots, u_n] \quad \text{for all } u_1, \dots, u_n \in \mathcal{U}.$$

Evaluating a template with κ behaves the same as alpha conversion [1, p. 69].

Theorem 3. For T an n -ary template, and $u_1, \dots, u_n \in \mathcal{U}$,

$$\llbracket T \rrbracket_\kappa(u_1, \dots, u_n) = \alpha(T)[u_1, \dots, u_n].$$

Assume now that two templates S and T are alpha equivalent. Then they have the same arity n , and for all \mathfrak{S} -algebras \mathcal{A} , and all valuations ν into \mathcal{A} , $\llbracket S \rrbracket_\nu = \llbracket T \rrbracket_\nu$. In particular, this is true for the de Bruijn abstraction algebra (for $\mathcal{U} = \mathcal{T}$) and the canonical valuation κ . Therefore, $\llbracket S \rrbracket_\kappa = \llbracket T \rrbracket_\kappa$, and

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha(S) &= \alpha(S)[\uparrow 0, \dots, \uparrow(n-1)] = \llbracket S \rrbracket_\kappa(\uparrow 0, \dots, \uparrow(n-1)) \\ &= \llbracket T \rrbracket_\kappa(\uparrow 0, \dots, \uparrow(n-1)) = \alpha(T)[\uparrow 0, \dots, \uparrow(n-1)] = \alpha(T). \end{aligned}$$

4 Abstraction Logic

According to Tao [3, p. 1], the material implication ‘ A implies B ’ can be thought of as ‘ B is at least as true as A ’. This is a very general view of implication, and as it turns out, perfectly suited to turn abstraction algebra into *abstraction logic*.

4.1 Logical Order and Truth Values

Definition 14. A *logical order* \mathcal{O} on a mathematical universe \mathcal{U} is a triple $\mathcal{O} = (\mathbb{T}, \preceq, |\cdot|)$, where

1. $\mathbb{T} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$ is a collection of **truth values**,
2. \preceq is a complete lattice on \mathbb{T} ,
3. $|\cdot|$ is a function from \mathcal{U} to \mathbb{T} and is the identity on \mathbb{T} .

The idea is that *any* value $u \in \mathcal{U}$ has a truth value $|u| \in \mathbb{T}$. Of course, $|u| = u$ if u is already in \mathbb{T} . For $u, v \in \mathcal{U}$, ‘ u implies v ’ is interpreted as $|u| \preceq |v|$.

A logical order is called **degenerate** if \mathbb{T} consists of exactly one element, which is equivalent to $true = false$. Here *true* is the top element of the complete lattice \mathbb{T} , and *false* is its bottom element. Note that \mathbb{T} cannot be empty, as $true \in \mathbb{T}$, hence every nondegenerate logical order will consist of at least two distinct elements, including *false* and *true*.

4.2 Bi-Heyting Logical Orders

General logical orders materialize ‘logical and’ and ‘logical or’ as lattice operations join and meet. We are not only interested in general logical orders, but also in orders where both the *join-infinite distributive law* and the *meet-infinite distributive law* hold. This allows us to also materialize ‘implication’ and ‘exclusion’. The **join-infinite distributive law** states that we can distribute a meet over arbitrary joins:

$$A \wedge \bigvee_{i \in I} B_i = \bigvee_{i \in I} (A \wedge B_i).$$

The **meet-infinite distributive law** distributes a join over arbitrary meets:

$$A \vee \bigwedge_{i \in I} B_i = \bigwedge_{i \in I} (A \vee B_i).$$

It is well-known [1, p. 80] that any complete lattice, in which both the join-infinite and meet-infinite distributive laws hold, can be turned into a **complete bi-Heyting algebra** by defining **implication** \rightarrow and **exclusion** \setminus via

$$\begin{aligned} A \rightarrow B &= \bigvee \{C \mid C \wedge A \preceq B\}, \\ B \setminus A &= \bigwedge \{C \mid C \vee A \succeq B\}. \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, in every complete bi-Heyting algebra, both the join-infinite and meet-infinite distributive laws hold.

Definition 15. We call a logical order **bi-Heyting** if its complete lattice is actually a bi-Heyting algebra, that is if both the join-infinite distributive law and the meet-infinite distributive law hold.

4.3 Formulas, Rules, and Sequents

A fundamental idea of abstraction logic is that *any term can also be viewed as a logical formula*.

Given a valuation ν into a \mathfrak{S} -algebra \mathcal{A} , the value of a \mathfrak{S} -term t is $\llbracket t \rrbracket_\nu$. Assuming some logical order, we can also view t as a formula, such that its truth value is $\llbracket t \rrbracket_\nu$. More generally, we can associate with any template T its *truth range*.

Definition 16. Let ν be a valuation into a \mathfrak{S} -algebra \mathcal{A} . We assume a logical order on the universe \mathcal{U} of \mathcal{A} . Then the **truth range** $\{T\}_\nu$ of an n -ary \mathfrak{S} -template T with respect to ν is the collection of truth values defined by

$$\{T\}_\nu = \{\llbracket T \rrbracket_\nu(u_1, \dots, u_n) \mid u_1, \dots, u_n \in \mathcal{U}\}.$$

For the special case of a term t , $\{t\}_\nu = \{\llbracket t \rrbracket_\nu\}$.

The notion of truth range allows us to formulate shorthands for the **infimum** $\bigwedge^\nu C$ and **supremum** $\bigvee^\nu C$ of the combined truth range of a collection C of templates with respect to a valuation ν :

$$\bigwedge^\nu C = \bigwedge \left(\bigcup_{T \in C} \{T\}_\nu \right), \quad \text{and} \quad \bigvee^\nu C = \bigvee \left(\bigcup_{T \in C} \{T\}_\nu \right).$$

Definition 17. A **\mathfrak{S} -sequent** is a pair (L, R) such that L and R are finite collections of \mathfrak{S} -templates modulo alpha equivalence. In these collections, we identify templates which are alpha equivalent. The elements of L are called **antecedents** or **premises**, and the elements of R are called **succedents**. A **\mathfrak{S} -rule** is a \mathfrak{S} -sequent which has exactly one succedent, which is a term. In this case, the succedent is also called the **conclusion**. A **\mathfrak{S} -formula** is a \mathfrak{S} -rule without any antecedents.

This means that essentially, a formula is just a term, and we can just write t instead of $(\{\}, \{t\})$.

Definition 18. Let ν be a valuation into a \mathfrak{S} -algebra \mathcal{A} . We assume a logical order on the universe of \mathcal{A} . A \mathfrak{S} -sequent (L, R) is called **valid for ν** iff

$$\bigwedge^{\nu} L \preceq \bigvee^{\nu} R.$$

Example 5. The sequent without any premises or succedents, the **empty sequent** (\emptyset, \emptyset) , is valid for any ν iff $\bigwedge \emptyset \preceq \bigvee \emptyset$, which can also be written $\bigvee \mathbb{T} \preceq \bigwedge \mathbb{T}$. Therefore, for any ν , (\emptyset, \emptyset) is valid iff the logical order is degenerate.

Example 6. A formula $(\{\}, \{t\})$ is valid for ν iff $\bigwedge \emptyset \preceq \bigvee \{t\}_{\nu}$, which is equivalent to $\llbracket t \rrbracket_{\nu} = \text{true}$. Analogously, $(\{t\}, \{\})$ is valid for ν iff $\llbracket t \rrbracket_{\nu} = \text{false}$.

Example 7. A sequent $(\{L_1, \dots, L_n\}, \{R_1, \dots, R_m\})$ is valid for ν iff

$$\left(\bigwedge^{\nu} L_1 \right) \wedge \dots \wedge \left(\bigwedge^{\nu} L_n \right) \preceq \left(\bigvee^{\nu} R_1 \right) \vee \dots \vee \left(\bigvee^{\nu} R_m \right).$$

4.4 Logic, Models, and Valuation Spaces

Definition 19. An **abstraction logic** \mathcal{L} is a signature \mathfrak{S} together with a collection \mathbb{A} of \mathfrak{S} -sequents. We call \mathbb{A} the **axioms** of \mathcal{L} .

Definition 20. A **valuation space** \mathcal{V} on \mathcal{A} , where \mathcal{U} is the universe of \mathcal{A} , is a collection of valuations into \mathcal{A} such that:

1. \mathcal{V} is not empty.
2. If $\nu \in \mathcal{V}$, $x \in \mathcal{X}$, and $u \in \mathcal{U}$, then also $\nu[x := u] \in \mathcal{V}$.
3. If $\nu \in \mathcal{V}$, and σ is a \mathfrak{S} -substitution, then also $\nu_{\sigma} \in \mathcal{V}$.

Definition 21. A **model** of an abstraction logic with signature \mathfrak{S} and axioms \mathbb{A} is a triple $\mathcal{M} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{V})$ where \mathcal{A} is a \mathfrak{S} -algebra, \mathcal{O} is a logical order on the universe of \mathcal{A} , and \mathcal{V} is a valuation space on \mathcal{A} , such that for all valuations $\nu \in \mathcal{V}$, every axiom in \mathbb{A} is valid for ν .

Clearly the space of all valuations into \mathcal{A} is a valuation space on \mathcal{A} . Models with this valuation space are called **standard**, all others are called **non-standard**. A model is called **degenerate** iff its logical order is degenerate. A model where the logical order is bi-Heyting is called a **bi-Heyting model**. Note that for each abstraction logic \mathcal{L} , there is a degenerate standard bi-Heyting model of \mathcal{L} with a singleton universe.

4.5 Sequent Calculus

A popular way in logic and computer science to present an inference rule is by listing its assumptions above a horizontal line and its conclusion below it. We can do the same for our sequents by listing their antecedents above the line, and

their succedents below it. For a sequent (L, R) such that $L = \{S_1, \dots, S_n\}$ and $R = \{T_1, \dots, T_m\}$, its **line notation** is²

$$\frac{S_1 \dots S_n}{T_1 \dots T_m}.$$

Line notation makes it possible to present theorems and proofs suggestively. We use the notation

$$\text{assumptions} \xrightarrow{\text{PROOFRULE}} \text{conclusion}$$

to express a particular proof rule. Mostly, assumptions and conclusion are simply sequents, understood as theorems. Figure 2a covers proofs by assumption, Figure 2b covers substitution, Figures 2c and 2e describe weakening, Figure 2d presents free variable elimination, and Figure 2f describes the cut rule(s). We call the proof system consisting of these proof rules **sequent calculus**.

All proof rules except those for cut are easily seen to be sound with respect to general models, based on our definition of validity and the properties of complete lattices. For example, the substitution rule SUBST in Figure 2b is sound: if the inequality holds for a valuation $\nu \in \mathcal{V}$, then applying a substitution σ is the same as evaluating the original inequality with respect to ν_σ , because of Theorem 2. And it is a property of valuation spaces that $\nu \in \mathcal{V}$ implies $\nu_\sigma \in \mathcal{V}$, so the inequality must also hold with respect to ν_σ .

For *cut* though, soundness requires the use of bi-Heyting models. In particular, the join-infinite distributive law is needed to prove the soundness of CUTSUCC, and the meet-infinite distributive law is needed to prove the soundness of CUTANTE. The technical report [1, p. 89, Soundness] contains all soundness proofs in detail.

Example 8. We can prove $\frac{x.x}{x}$ as follows:

$$x \text{ is a template} \xrightarrow{\text{ASSUME}} \frac{x}{x} \xrightarrow{\text{BINDANTE}} \frac{x.x}{x} \xrightarrow{\text{FREESUCC}} \frac{x.x}{x}.$$

Similarly, we can prove $\frac{x}{x.x}$ by using BINDSUCC and FREEANTE instead.

4.6 Natural Deduction

Sequent calculus is beautiful in its symmetry, but requires bi-Heyting models instead of just general models. By restricting sequent calculus to *rules only* instead of general sequents, we obtain what we call **natural deduction**. Natural deduction is a special case of sequent calculus as every natural deduction proof and theorem is also a sequent calculus proof and theorem. But it is also more general than sequent calculus in that it is sound for general models, not just bi-Heyting models. Because natural deduction operates exclusively on rules, all XXXSUCC proof rules become useless, leaving only AXIOM, ASSUME, SUBST,

² Of course, in case the sequent is a formula, we may omit the line altogether.

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{S_1 \dots S_n}{T_1 \dots T_m} \in \mathbb{A} \xrightarrow{\text{AXIOM}} \frac{S_1 \dots S_n}{T_1 \dots T_m} \\
 T \text{ is any template} \xrightarrow{\text{ASSUME}} \frac{T}{T} \\
 \text{(a) Proof by } \textit{assumption}
 \end{array}
 \qquad
 \begin{array}{c}
 \frac{S_1 \dots S_n}{T_1 \dots T_m} \xrightarrow{\text{SUBST}} \frac{S_1/\sigma \dots S_n/\sigma}{T_1/\sigma \dots T_m/\sigma} \\
 \text{(b) Proof by } \textit{substitution}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{S_1 \dots S_n}{T_1 \dots T_m} \xrightarrow{\text{ADDANTE}} \frac{S_1 \dots S_n \ A}{T_1 \dots T_m} \\
 \frac{S_1 \dots S_n}{T_1 \dots T_m} \xrightarrow{\text{ADDSUCC}} \frac{S_1 \dots S_n}{T_1 \dots T_m \ A} \\
 \text{(c) Proof by } \textit{weakening} \text{ (ADD)}
 \end{array}
 \qquad
 \begin{array}{c}
 \frac{x \ S_1 \dots S_n}{T_1 \dots T_m} \xrightarrow{\text{FREEANTE}} \frac{S_1 \dots S_n}{T_1 \dots T_m} \\
 \frac{S_1 \dots S_n}{x \ T_1 \dots T_m} \xrightarrow{\text{FREESUCC}} \frac{S_1 \dots S_n}{T_1 \dots T_m} \\
 \text{where the variable } x \text{ does not appear free} \\
 \text{with arity 0 in } S_1 \dots S_n \text{ or } T_1 \dots T_m. \\
 \text{(d) Proof by } \textit{free variable elimination}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{S_1 \dots S_n \ (y_1 \dots y_l \ t)}{T_1 \dots T_m} \xrightarrow{\text{BINDANTE}} \frac{S_1 \dots S_n \ (x_1 \dots x_k \ t)}{T_1 \dots T_m} \\
 \frac{S_1 \dots S_n}{T_1 \dots T_m \ (y_1 \dots y_l \ t)} \xrightarrow{\text{BINDSUCC}} \frac{S_1 \dots S_n}{T_1 \dots T_m \ (x_1 \dots x_k \ t)} \\
 \text{where no variable in } \{y_1, \dots, y_l\} \setminus \{x_1, \dots, x_k\} \\
 \text{occurs free with arity 0 in } t \\
 \text{(e) Proof by } \textit{weakening} \text{ (BIND)}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{S_1 \dots S_n \ (x_1 \dots x_k \ c)}{R_1 \dots R_u}, \frac{T_1 \dots T_m}{c \ Q_1 \dots Q_v} \xrightarrow{\text{CUTANTE}} \frac{S_1 \dots S_n \ T_1 \dots T_m}{R_1 \dots R_u \ Q_1 \dots Q_v} \\
 \frac{S_1 \dots S_n}{R_1 \dots R_u \ (x_1 \dots x_k \ c)}, \frac{c \ T_1 \dots T_m}{Q_1 \dots Q_v} \xrightarrow{\text{CUTSUCC}} \frac{S_1 \dots S_n \ T_1 \dots T_m}{R_1 \dots R_u \ Q_1 \dots Q_v} \\
 \text{where no } x_i \text{ occurs as a free variable with arity 0 in} \\
 T_1 \dots T_m \text{ or } Q_1 \dots Q_v \\
 \text{(f) Proof by } \textit{cut}
 \end{array}$$

Fig. 2: Sequent calculus proof rules

ADDANTE, FREEANTE, BINDANTE and CUTANTE as proof rules. Furthermore, CUTANTE turns into a *rule of inference*, INFER:

$$\frac{S_1 \dots S_n \quad (x_1 \dots x_k \cdot c)}{r}, \quad \frac{T_1 \dots T_m}{c} \stackrel{\text{INFER}}{\rightsquigarrow} \frac{S_1 \dots S_n \quad T_1 \dots T_m}{r},$$

where no x_i occurs as a free variable with arity 0 in $T_1 \dots T_m$. It turns out that INFER is sound for general models [1, p. 92, Lemma 3.11], which means that natural deduction as a whole is sound for general models.

Natural deduction has another advantage: we know that it is complete.

4.7 Consistency and Completeness

Definition 22. We call an abstraction logic **inconsistent** iff all formulas are theorems. An abstraction logic which is not inconsistent is called **consistent**.

An abstraction logic is called **complete** iff every formula which is valid is also a theorem.

Theorem 4. For any variable x , an abstraction logic is inconsistent iff the formula x is a theorem.

Theorem 5. An inconsistent abstraction logic has only degenerate models. If the abstraction logic is complete, then it is inconsistent iff it has only degenerate models.

Both theorems follow almost immediately. Their proofs can also be found in [1].

4.8 The Rasiowa Model

Given a consistent abstraction logic \mathcal{L} with signature \mathfrak{S} and axioms \mathbb{A} , such that all axioms are rules, and such that there is at least one theorem which is a formula, we build a non-degenerate bi-Heyting model \mathcal{R} for it which we call the **Rasiowa model for \mathcal{L}** . The name has been chosen because abstraction logic and its semantics have been inspired by Rasiowa's book on her algebraic approach to non-classical logics [4]. Constructing the Rasiowa model is similar to the construction of the Lindenbaum-Tarski algebra in other logics. The abstraction algebra of \mathcal{R} is the de Bruijn abstraction algebra for \mathfrak{S} , with universe $\mathcal{U} = \mathcal{T}_0$. To define the logical order of \mathcal{R} , we pick an arbitrary \mathfrak{S} -term F such that F is not a theorem of \mathcal{L} . This is possible because \mathcal{L} is consistent. Furthermore, we pick an arbitrary \mathfrak{S} -term T such that T is a theorem of \mathcal{L} . This is possible because there is at least one theorem which is a formula. The collection of truth values is $\mathbb{T} = \{false, true\}$, where $false = \alpha(F)$ and $true = \alpha(T)$. Clearly, $false \neq true$, because otherwise F would be a theorem. The truth value $|u|$ of $u \in \mathcal{U}$ is then defined as *true* if there is a theorem t with $\alpha(t) = u$, and *false* otherwise.

Any total \mathfrak{S} -substitution σ induces a valuation $\sigma^* = \kappa_\sigma$ [1, Definition 3.24 and Lemma 3.34]. Such a valuation σ^* is called **regular**. We then define the valuation space \mathcal{V} of \mathcal{R} as the space of all regular valuations. It is straightforward

to see that \mathcal{V} fulfils all three criteria of valuation spaces. First, κ is a regular valuation, so \mathcal{V} is not empty [1, Lemma 3.31]. Second, $(\sigma^*)[x := u] = (\sigma[x := t])^*$, where $u = \alpha(t)$, so \mathcal{V} is closed under updates [1, Lemma 3.32]. Third, $(\sigma^*)_\tau = (\tau\sigma)^*$, so \mathcal{V} is closed under substitutions [1, Lemma 3.36].

It remains to be seen that all axioms \mathbb{A} of \mathcal{L} hold in \mathcal{R} . We will show this here for axioms which are formulas. For the general case of rules, we refer the reader to [1, Lemma 3.39]. So let $t \in \mathbb{A}$ be a formula. We need to show that $\llbracket t \rrbracket_\nu = \text{true}$ for all regular valuations ν . Because ν is regular, there is a total substitution σ with $\nu = \sigma^*$. Therefore $\llbracket t \rrbracket_\nu = \llbracket t \rrbracket_{\sigma^*} = \llbracket t \rrbracket_{\kappa_\sigma} = \llbracket t/\sigma \rrbracket_\kappa = |\alpha(t/\sigma)| = \text{true}$. Here we made use of Theorem 2 and the fact that evaluation with κ behaves like alpha conversion (Theorem 3).

Theorem 6. *Let \mathcal{L} be an abstraction logic such that all its axioms are rules, and such that some formula is a theorem. Then \mathcal{L} is complete.*

Proof. If \mathcal{L} is inconsistent, then it is trivially complete. So assume \mathcal{L} is consistent. Then we can construct its Rasiowa model \mathcal{R} . Given a formula t which is valid in all models of \mathcal{L} , it must be valid in particular in \mathcal{R} , and in particular with respect to the canonical valuation κ . Therefore $|\alpha(t)| = \llbracket t \rrbracket_\kappa = \text{true}$, which means that t is a theorem.

Theorem 6 says that all abstraction logics for natural deduction are complete, as long as they have at least one theorem which is a formula. This last side condition can be removed with the help of the *deduction theorem* [1, p. 115, Theorem 3.8]. Therefore, natural deduction is complete.

5 Conclusion

We conclude with an example of a concrete abstraction logic consisting of 8 axioms (2 proper rules, 6 formulas) for intuitionistic predicate calculus, writing ‘ $A \Rightarrow B$ ’ for ‘*implies* AB ’, ‘ $\forall x. A[x]$ ’ for ‘*forall* ($x. A[x]$)’ and ‘ $x = y$ ’ for ‘*equals* xy ’. The logic is consistent; just use the two-valued Heyting algebra as a non-degenerate model. It is complete; because all axioms are rules. More examples of abstraction logic can be found at [5], such as minimal logic and thus paraconsistent logic; classical predicate logic; Peano arithmetic with induction and recursion; and lambda calculus. They demonstrate the suitability of abstraction logic not only as a logic, but also as a *logical framework*.

MODUS PONENS	$\frac{A \Rightarrow B \quad A}{B}$,
GENERALIZATION	$\frac{x. A[x]}{\forall x. A[x]}$,
IMPLICATION ₁	$A \Rightarrow (B \Rightarrow A)$,
IMPLICATION ₂	$(A \Rightarrow (B \Rightarrow C)) \Rightarrow ((A \Rightarrow B) \Rightarrow (A \Rightarrow C))$,
UNIVERSAL ₁	$(\forall x. A[x]) \Rightarrow A[x]$,
UNIVERSAL ₂	$(\forall x. A \Rightarrow B[x]) \Rightarrow (A \Rightarrow (\forall x. B[x]))$,
EQUALITY ₁	$x = x$,
EQUALITY ₂	$(x = y) \Rightarrow (A[x] \Rightarrow A[y])$.

References

1. Steven Obua. *Abstraction Logic (Founder's Edition): A New Foundation for Reasoning, Computing, and Understanding*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15042623>, March 2025.
2. Helena Rasiowa. *Introduction to Modern Mathematics*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2013-0-11892-2>, North-Holland 1973.
3. Terence Tao. *Compactness and Contradiction*. <https://doi.org/10.1090/mbk/081>, American Mathematical Society, 2013.
4. Helena Rasiowa. *An Algebraic Approach to Non-Classical Logics*. North-Holland Publishing Company / Elsevier, May 1974.
5. *Practal Flyweight*. <https://practal.com/flyweight>.